

Isocarbostyrils. Part I. Conversion of 8-Alkoxyisocarbostyril-3-Carboxylic Acids into the Related Hydroxy-Esters by Pseudo-Rearrangement*

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On heating 5,8- or 7,8-dimethoxyisocarbostyril-3-carboxylic acids, an unusual intermolecular trans-alkylation takes place resulting in the formations of the related 8-hydroxymethyl esters. This finding invalidates some conclusions of Bain *et al.*¹ and Linevich, with regard to 7,8-dimethoxyisocarbostyril. Similar alkylation results in the case of 7-methoxy-8-ethoxyisocarbostyril-3-carboxylic acid. A mechanism of the trans-alkylation has been suggested.

The orthoformates, isolated by King and Stiller^{2a} have now been assigned structures on basis of NMR spectra.

Amines and ammonia are known to react with isocoumarins furnishing isocarbostyrils³. Several isocoumarins, prepared in connection with synthesis of isochromenes, have been converted into the corresponding isocarbostyrils by cold or hot ethanolic ammonia. In the case of 5,8-dimethoxy-isocoumarin, the action of cold ammonia afforded the intermediate (I) which lost elements of water by application of heat or by the action of acids, providing 5,8-dimethoxyisocarbostyril (II). The intermediate arises by ring scission following the nucleophilic attack of ammonia and by subsequent aldol condensation of the resulting amidoaldehyde.

Although 3-benzoyl-7,8-dimethoxyisocoumarin was converted quantitatively into the related isocarbostyril³, 7,8-dimethoxyisocarbostyril (VIII), now prepared from 7,8-dimethoxyisocoumarin (XVII), did not agree with the physical constants of the same compound described by Bain *et al.*¹, who claimed to have obtained 7,8-dimethoxyisocarbostyril, m.p. 233° from 7,8-dimethoxyisocarbostyril-3-carboxylic acid (VII) by the action of heat.

* A preliminary communication appeared in *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1965, 27, 2281.

1. Gabriel, *Chem. Ber.*, 1903, 36, 570.

2. Kanevskaya *et al. Obshch. Khim. Akad. Nauk, USSR* 1953, 2, 1493; *Chem. Abstr.*, 1955, 49, 5477.

3. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 105, 2398.

This work was repeated and confirmed by Linevich* who prepared the acid by a slightly modified method. The correctness of structure of our isocarbostyryl has been confirmed by the similarity of UV absorption spectrum with known isocarbostyryls (*vide* experimental) and by its conversion into 7, 8-dimethoxyisoquinoline (III) via the 1-chloro derivative. The isoquinoline was also secured by the acid-catalysed cyclisation of 2,3-dimethoxybenzylidene-aminocetal (IV)⁵. It has not been possible to effect the reverse conversion, i.e., conversion of the isoquinoline into the isocarbostyryl. Attempted hydroxylation of the former with strong alkali led to extensive decomposition; the related *N*-oxide could not be converted by standard procedure⁶ to the 7, 8-dimethoxy 2-acetoxyisoquinolins. Also, we failed to effect a rearrangement of the phthalide (V) into (VIII).

Likewise 6, 7-dimethoxyisocarbostyryl, prepared from the related isocoumarin, was converted into 6,7-dimethoxyisoquinoline and yet 6, 7-dimethoxyisocarbostyryl was obtained by the normal decarboxylation of 6, 7-dimethoxyisocarbostyryl-3-carboxylic acid. The latter was secured by standard method from *m*-opianic acid by the oxazolone route or from the related isocoumarin acid, secured from *m*-opianic acid by reaction with ethyl bromomalonate⁷.

The above experiments lead to the conclusion that the so-called 7, 8-dimethoxyisocarbostyryl, isolated by Bain *et al.*⁵, must have a different structure and a reinvestigation was in order. 7, 8-dimethoxy isocarbostyryl-3-carboxylic acid, now prepared by the action of ammonia on the corresponding isocoumarin, agreed with the product of Bain *et al.*⁵ By the action of heat on the compound, the so-called 7, 8-dimethoxyisocarbostyryl, m.p. 233°, was isolated in 40-50% yield. The compound was found to be isomeric with the original acid and contained two methoxyl groups, thus at first arousing a suspicion that the compound is the anhydride (VI). The NMR spectrum was less informative, as a good spectrum could not be obtained on account of the low solubility of the compound in suitable solvents. It clearly showed, however, presence of two methoxyl groups at δ 5.95 and 6.05 τ . The UV

4. Linevich, *Zhur. Obshch. Khim.*, 1958, 29, 2510; *Chem. Abs.*, 1959, 53, 3222.

5. Perkin, jun., and Robinson; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 108, 2382.

6. Michael *et al.*; *J. Org. Chem.* 1956, 21, 1337.

7. Duro and Condorelli, *Chem. Abs.*, 1963, 58, 9011.

spectrum of the compound was significantly different from methoxylated isocarbostyrils. The IR spectrum in chloroform showed clearly the presence of an associated hydroxyl (2.96 μ) and an ester group (5.80 μ). On methylation with methyl iodide and potassium carbonate, the compound afforded

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| (VII) R=Me; R'=COOH; R''=H. | (XIa) R=R''=H; R'=COOMe; |
| (VIII) R=Me; R'=R''=H. | (XIb) R=R''=H; R'=COOEt. |
| (IX) R=R''=Me; R'=COOMe | (XII) R=R''=H; R'=COOH. |
| (X) R=Me; R'=COOMe; R''=H. | (XIII) R=R''=R''=H. |
| | (XIV) R=Et; R'=COOH; R''=H. |
| | (XV) R=H; R'=COOH; R''=H. |

- (XVI) R=R'=H
 (XVII) R=Me; R'=H.
 (XVIIIa) R=Me; R'=COOH.
 (XVIIIb) R=Et; R'=COOH.
 (XIX) R=Et; R'=H.

(XX)

- (XXI) R=Me; R'=H.
 (XXII) R=H; R'=Me.

methyl *N*-methyl-7, 8-dimethoxyisocarbostyril-3-carboxylate (IX), identical with the product obtained by the methylation of methyl 7, 8-dimethoxyisocarbostyril-3-carboxylate (X). The NMR spectrum showed nine protons as three singlets at 6.00, 6.05, 6.08 τ and *N*-methyl group at 6.26 τ . On these grounds, the product, m.p. 233°, of Bain *et al*⁸ must be regarded as methyl 7-methoxy-8-hydroxyisocarbostyril-3-carboxylate (XIa) and this was confirmed by hydrolysis with aqueous potassium carbonate to the related acid (XII) which on decarboxylation with copper bronze in boiling quinoline furnished 7-methoxy-8-hydroxyisocarbostyril (XIII) (3 protons at 6.00 τ due to 7-methoxyl group) and this was verified by an independent synthesis of the compound from 7-methoxy-8-hydroxyisocoumarin (XVI).

Formation of the ester (XIa) from (VII) by mere heating is an unexpected result. It is a case of pseudo-rearrangement arising from intermolecular *trans*-alkylation involving the 8-methoxyl group. We have drawn attention to a similar case of *trans*-methylation in the isocoumarin series⁸. That the rearrangement is due to an intermolecular reaction can

be demonstrated by heating the acid with phenylacetic acid, resulting in the formation of the phenol (XII) and methyl phenyl acetate. The methoxyl at the 8-position is labile on account of the participation of the neighbouring carbonyl group and we suggest the following mechanism.

In a further study of this curious rearrangement, 7-methoxy-8-ethoxyisocarbostyryl-3-carboxylic acid (XIV) was prepared by a standard route³ from 2-ethoxy-3-methoxybenzoic acid through 3-ethoxy-4-methoxyphthalide (XX) and the corresponding phthalaldehydic acid. Preparation of (XX) in our hands did not arise any difficulty although contrary results were recorded.⁹ By the action of heat this acid was again converted into ethyl 7-methoxy-8-hydroxyisocarbostyryl-3-carboxylate (XIb) by transalkylation. By further extension, 5,8-dimethoxyisocarbostyryl-3-carboxylic acid (XXI) was prepared from the related isocoumarin acid (*vide* experimental) and as expected, this compound as well underwent pseudo-rearrangement providing the ester (XXII). Incidentally, the 8-alkoxy group in the isocarbostyryl is more labile than in the corresponding isocoumarin series.

7-methoxy-8-ethoxyisocoumarin-3-carboxylic acid (XVIIIb), for example, afforded on heating a mixture of 7-methoxy-8-hydroxyisocoumarin (XVI) and 7-methoxy-8-ethoxyisocoumarin (XIX). It may be recalled⁹ that 7,8-dimethoxyisocoumarin-3-carboxylic acid (XVIIIa) furnished on heating a mixture of four products, viz., 7, 8-dimethoxyisocoumarin, 7-methoxy-8-hydroxyisocoumarin, methyl 7-methoxy-8-hydroxyisocoumarin-3-carboxylate, and methyl 7, 8-dimethoxyisocoumarin-3-carboxylate. Formation of these products is in line with the mechanism of transalkylation suggested above.

Finally, we take this opportunity to mention the synthesis of isocarbostyryl-3-carboxylic acid by way of oxazolones developed by Bain *et al*.¹¹ and studied later by Stiller¹⁰

9. Manske and Ledingham, *Canad. J. Res.*, 1944, 22B, 115.

10. Stiller, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 473.

(of. King and Stiller^{10a}) who isolated a product, $C_{10}H_8NO(OCH_3)_3$, by the hydrolysis of the oxazolone (XXIII) with methanolic alkali. They regarded the compound as (XXIVa) or (XXIVb), of which the former was favoured. The NMR spectrum of the compound showed nine protons as a singlet at the aliphatic methoxyl region (6.70 τ) and one proton at 3.14 τ (NH) and thus confirms the structure (XXIVa). We have similarly prepared the orthoformate (XXV). This compound also showed nine protons at 6.70 τ , six methoxyl protons at 5.99 τ , and 6.04 τ and one proton at 3.30 τ (NH), which is in agreement with structure (XXV). This orthoformate smoothly passed into the ester (X) on treatment with acid.

The orthoformate (XXV) when refluxed with methyl iodide and potassium carbonate in acetone yielded (XXVI) which on treatment with acid provided (IX). This lends further support to the structure of (IX) and proves conclusively that on methylation with methyl iodide, the isocarbostyrils yield *N*-methylisocarbostyrils.

EXPERIMENTAL

7, 8-Dimethoxyisocarbostyril-3-carboxylic Acid.—7, 8-dimethoxyisocoumarin-3-carboxylic acid (2.0 g.) was taken with methanolic ammonia (10 ml saturated at 0°) and left overnight in a pressure bottle. Next day, the solution was worked up to provide 7,8-dimethoxyisocarbostyril-3-carboxylic acid in quantitative yield, crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m. p. 261°. Mixed m. p. with authentic specimen obtained by the method of Bain *et al.*⁹ remained unchanged (carboxyl absorption at 5.82 μ).

5,8-Dimethoxyisocarbostyril.—5,8-Dimethoxyisocoumarin (*vide infra*) (0.1 g.) was taken with ethanolic ammonia (5 ml. saturated at 0°) and left for 12 hr. The isocoumarin

*All m. p.'s are uncorrected. Unless otherwise mentioned the IR spectra were determined in nujol suspension. The NMR spectra were taken in $CDCl_3$ in varian A-60 apparatus.

10a. King and Stiller, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 466.

soon went into solution and in about 5-6 hr. colorless crystals of (I) began to separate. On evaporating the solvent the residue was crystallised from ethanol in colorless shining crystals, m.p. 191° (gas evolution) (-OH absorption at 2.80 μ), remelting at 214-15° with the formation of 5,8-dimethoxyisocarbostyryl.

On heating compound (I), m.p. 101°, 5, 8-dimethoxyisocarbostyryl was obtained, crystallising from a large volume of benzene in plates, m.p. 214-15°. (Found: C, 63.9; H, 5.5. $C_{11}H_{11}O_3N$ requires C, 64.3; H, 5.4%). The picrate crystallised from ethanol in yellow needles, m.p. 176-77°.

Compound (I) when recrystallised from glacial acetic acid yielded the isocarbostyryl, m.p. 214-15°.

7-Methoxyisocarbostyryl.—A mixture of 7-methoxyisocoumarin (0.1 g.) and methanolic ammonia (3 ml, saturated at 0°) was kept in a pressure bottle for 20 hr. On working up, 7-methoxyisocarbostyryl was obtained as prisms from ethanol, m.p. 206°. $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 276 m μ and 339 m μ . (Found: C, 68.37; H, 5.10. $C_{10}H_9O_2N$ requires C, 68.58; H, 5.14%).

The picrate, m.p. 156° separated as yellow needles from ethanol. (Found: N, 13.62. $C_{10}H_9O_2N.C_6H_5N_3O_7$, requires N, 13.87%).

Methyl 7-Methoxy-8-hydroxyisocarbostyryl-3-carboxylate.—7,8-dimethoxyisocarbostyryl-3-carboxylic acid (0.1 g.) was heated to 270-85° in a metal bath for 20 minutes and sublimed under vacuum. The reaction product was thoroughly washed with sodium bicarbonate and crystallised from glacial acetic acid in almost colorless wooly needles (0.05 g.) m.p. 233° (lit.³, m.p. 233°) $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{CHCl}_3}$ 225,352 and 367 m μ . IR (CHCl_3): 5.80 μ (ester carbonyl), 2.96 (phenolic) (Found: C, 57.0; H 4.5; OMe, 23.0. $C_{11}H_{11}O_5N$ requires C, 57.8; H, 4.4; OMe, 24.9%).

The compound showed a green ferric reaction and did not afford any picrate.

Methyl N-Methyl-7,8-dimethoxyisocarbostyryl-3-carboxylate.—To the foregoing compound (0.06 g.) in dry acetone (25 ml), freshly baked potassium carbonate (2 g.) and methyl iodide (2 c.c.) were added and the contents gently refluxed overnight. The reaction mixture was filtered and the acetone evaporated. The residue on treatment with water afforded a cream-coloured product, m.p. 159-60°. It was recrystallised from methanol in colorless prisms, m.p. 160-61°. (Found: C, 60.2; H, 6.0. $C_{14}H_{13}O_5N$ requires C, 60.6; H, 5.4%) Ester carbonyl absorption at 5.83 μ . The compound did not respond to ferric reaction.

Alternative Method.—7,8-dimethoxyisocarbostyryl-3-carboxylic acid (0.25 g.) was esterified by diazomethane (from 0.3 g. of nitrosomethylurea). The ester (m.p. 190°, lit.⁴, m.p. 195°) (0.23 g.) was taken in dry acetone (25 ml); freshly baked potassium carbonate (3 g.) and methyl iodide (3 ml.) were added and the mixture refluxed overnight. On working up in usual manner a crystalline product, m.p. 158-9° was obtained (0.2 g.) which was recrystallised from methanol; m.p. and mixed m.p. with the above sample 160-61°.

The same compound was also obtained by methylating 7,8-dimethoxyisocarbostyryl-3-carboxylic acid by potassium carbonate and methyl iodide but the yield was poor and much of the acid was recovered as potassium salt.

Methyl 7, 8-Dimethoxyisocarbostyryl-3-orthoformate.—The 2-phenyl-4-(2'-methoxy-carbonyl-3', 4'-dimethoxy)-benzylidene-5-oxazolone(1.7 g.), obtained by the method of

Bain *et al.*³, was taken with absolute methanol (33 ml.) and KOH (1.6g.) and refluxed for 3.5. hr. White crystalline particles separated within $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. of the commencement of the reaction. The mixture was cooled and filtered. The residue on treatment with HCl provided 7, 8-dimethoxyisocarbostyryl-3-carboxylic acid which was recrystallised from acetic acid; m.p. and mixed m.p. 260-61°.

The filtrate was concentrated to half its bulk under reduced pressure and water (ca. 40 ml.) was added to the cooled solution. The solution was neutralised with HCl (dil.) and kept overnight when white shining crystals of the methyl 7,8-dimethoxyisocarbostyryl-3-orthoformate (0.62 g.) m.p. 150-60°, were obtained. This on recrystallisation with methanol and hot water furnished colorless plates, m.p. 163-64°. (Found: C, 57.9; H, 6.6. $C_{13}H_{16}O_6N$ requires C, 58.2; H, 6.1%). This product on admixture depressed the m.p. of the methyl *N*-methyl-7,8-dimethoxyisocarbostyryl-3-carboxylate.

The orthoformate was treated with HCl (dil.) and warmed on a water bath for 5 min. Colorless needles of the methyl 7,8-dimethoxyisocarbostyryl-3-carboxylate was quantitatively obtained, m.p. and mixed m.p. with the authentic sample 198-99° (no depression).

Methyl N-Methyl-7, 8-dimethoxyisocarbostyryl-3-carboxylate.—The orthoformate (0.05 g.) in dry acetone (3 ml.), freshly baked potassium carbonate (1.0 g.), and methyl iodide (3 c.c.) were refluxed overnight. After working up the solution as usual, *methyl N-methyl 7, 8-dimethoxyisocarbostyryl-3-orthoformate* was obtained as an oil which slowly solidified, m.p. 111-12°. Recrystallisation from methanol furnished slightly coloured needles, m.p. 117-18°. (Found: C, 59.2; H, 6.9. $C_{18}H_{21}O_6N$ requires C, 59.4; H, 6.5%).

The aforesaid product was treated with a few drops of HCl (conc.) when *methyl-N methyl-7,8-dimethoxyisocarbostyryl-3-carboxylate* was obtained, m.p. and mixed m.p. with the authentic sample, 160-61° (no depression).

7-Methoxy-8-hydroxyisocarbostyryl-3-carboxylic Acid.—Methyl 7-methoxy-8-hydroxyisocarbostyryl-3-carboxylate (0.6 g.) was taken with aqueous potassium carbonate (30 ml., 10%) and heated on a steam bath for 3 hr. On cooling, silky white needles of the potassium salt separated, which on acidification with HCl (conc.) afforded 7-methoxy-8-hydroxyisocarbostyryl-3-carboxylic acid (0.48 g.) (I.R. absorption at 5.95 μ). This was purified by vacuum sublimation at 270-80°. The sample on recrystallisation from *n*-butanol melted at 314-15°. (Found: C, 56.1; H, 4.1. $C_{11}H_{10}O_5N$ requires C, 56.1; H, 3.8%).

The acid (0.04 g.) was added to an ethereal solution of diazomethane (from 0.2 g. of nitrosomethylurea). Instantaneous evolution of nitrogen took place and a colorless product was obtained which was recrystallised from ethanol in colorless wooly needles, m.p. 233°. Mixed m.p. with methyl 7-methoxy-8-hydroxyisocarbostyryl-3-carboxylate remained undepressed.

Reaction of 7, 8-Dimethoxyisocarbostyryl-3-carboxylic Acid with Phenylacetic Acid. A mixture of (7,8-Dimethoxyisocarbostyryl-3-carboxylic acid (0.2 g.) and phenylacetic acid (2 g.) was refluxed very gently for 1 hr., cooled, and extracted with ether; the extract was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution, followed by water and dried ($MgSO_4$). Removal of the solvent left the residue as an oil having typical odour of esters. It was distilled in a bulb under reduced pressure and the distillate provided superimposable IR curves with methyl phenylacetate.

The ether-insoluble portion showed a bluish green ferric reaction and had m.p. 310-11°, and was methylated by diazomethane to a compound, m.p. 232-33°, mixed m.p. with methyl 7-methoxy-8-hydroxyisocarbostyryl-3-carboxylate remained undepressed.

7-Methoxy-8-hydroxyisocarbostyryl

(i) 7-Methoxy-8-hydroxyisocarbostyryl-3-carboxylic acid was taken with copper-bronze (0.1 g.) and quinoline (3 ml.) and refluxed for 3 hr. The quinoline was removed by steam distillation and the residual solution was extracted with ether (3 × 10 ml.). The extract was successively washed with HCl (very dilute), saturated sodium bicarbonate solution, and water; it was dried over MgSO₄. On evaporation, 7-methoxy-8-hydroxyisocarbostyryl left was repeatedly crystallised from benzene in fine colorless needles, m.p. 210-11°. (Found: C, 62.7; H, 4.8; N, 7.2. C₁₀H₉O₃N requires C, 62.8; H, 4.7; N, 7.3% $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$. 225, 285, 295, 352 m μ .)

The compound showed a blue ferric reaction and afforded chocolate needles of the picrate, m.p. 195-96°. (Found: N, 13.2. C₁₀H₉O₃N.C₆H₃N₃O₇, requires N, 13.3%.)

Decarboxylation of 7, 8-dimethoxyisocarbostyryl-3-carboxylic acid with copper bronze-quinoline also afforded the same compound; m.p. and mixed m.p. 210-11°.

(ii) 7-Methoxy-8-hydroxyisocoumarin⁹ (m.p. 150-51°) (0.1 g.) was heated with ethanolic ammonia at 140° for 8 hr. or left in a pressure bottle for 12 hr. The ethanolic solution on evaporation left 7-methoxy-8-hydroxyisocarbostyryl, m.p. 208°, in quantitative yield. It was recrystallised from ethanol in shining plates; m.p. and mixed m.p. with the above sample was 210-11°.

7, 8-Dimethoxyisocarbostyryl.—7,8-Dimethoxyisocoumarin⁹ (0.08 g.) was taken with ethanolic ammonia (10 c.c., saturated at 0°) and left in a pressure bottle. On working up in the usual manner, the product slowly solidified, m.p. 171°. It was recrystallised from benzene-light petroleum in colorless plates, m.p. 178-79°. (Found: C, 63.80; H, 5.5. C₁₁H₁₁O₃N requires C, 64.30; H, 5.4%) $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 281 (log ϵ 4.18), 292 (log ϵ 4.06), and 349 m μ . (log ϵ 3.85). The picrate, m.p. 150-51° was obtained in lemon yellow needles, from ethanol. (Found: C, 47.1; H, 3.2; N, 13.1. C₁₁H₁₁O₃N.C₆H₃O₇N₃, requires C, 47.0; H, 3.2; N, 12.9%.)

7, 8-Dimethoxyisoquinoline.—7,8-Dimethoxyisocarbostyryl (0.02 g.) was taken with POCl₃ (1.0 ml.) and refluxed for 4 hr. Excess of the oxychloride was removed in vacuum and the residue treated with crushed ice. The solution was extracted with ether; the extract was dried (MgSO₄) and evaporated to provide 1-chloro-7,8-dimethoxyisoquinoline as an impure oil. The chloro compound was taken with methanol (2 ml.), a drop of methanolic KOH was added, and hydrogenated over palladised charcoal (30%). Reduction was complete in a few minutes. The solution on working up in the usual manner afforded 7,8-dimethoxyisoquinoline, characterised as the picrate obtained as fine yellow needles, m.p. 200-201°, undepressed on admixture with an authentic specimen prepared from 7,8-dimethoxyisoquinoline⁸. (Found: N, 12.9. C₁₁H₁₁O₂N. C₆H₃O₇N₃, requires N, 13.4%.)

Attempted alternative Synthesis of 7, 8-Dimethoxyisocarbostyryl.

6,7-Dimethoxy-8-nitromethylphthalide.—To a mixture of opanic acid (2.7 g.) and

nitromethane (1.1 g.), dissolved in methanol (13.5 ml.), and cooled to -5° , NaOH solution (1.7 g. in 6 ml. water) was added dropwise with shaking. The mixture after stirring for 1 hr. at the room temperature was poured into 5*N*-HCl (10.8 ml), when the phthalide (2.60 g.) separated. It was crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 161-62° (lit.¹¹, m.p. 163°). Found: C, 52.08; H, 4.40. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{11}O_6N$: C, 52.18; H, 4.34%.

Reduction. The foregoing compound (0.5 g.), dissolved in ethanol (20 c.c.), was added to a solution of stannous chloride (1.9 g.) in HCl (conc., 8 ml) and the mixture kept overnight at 0° when the tin complex (0.4 g.) separated as colorless needles. The crystals were collected and washed with minimum volume of ethanol.

Decomposition of the Tin complex.—The preceding compound (0.4 g.) was refluxed with *N*-NaOH solution (40 ml.), cooled and filtered; the filtrate was acidified with HCl (conc.). The product after evaporation to dryness was crystallised from water, when the free amine hydrochloride m.p. 248-50° (lit.¹¹, m.p. 245°) was obtained as light brown needles. I.R. spectrum 4.94 μ (NR_4^+). It dissolved freely in sodium bicarbonate solution and in NaOH solution. (Found: C, 50.71; H, 5.41; N, 5.35. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{11}O_4N$ Cl: C, 50.87; H, 5.39; N, 5.39%.)

Attempted Conversion of 7, 8-Dimethoxyisoquinoline.—7, 8-Dimethoxyisoquinoline (3. g.), taken in glacial acetic acid (7 ml.) and hydrogen peroxide (2.3) was heated in an oil bath at 60-70°. After 3 hr. more hydrogen peroxide (1.9 ml.) was added and further heated at constant temperature for 12 hr. The solution was evaporated under reduced pressure on a water bath and the process repeated after adding water (2.5 ml.). The thick gummy residue left was crystallised, m.p. 123-24° (3.3 g.). The mass was treated with a slurry made of excess potassium carbonate and water and left overnight, filtered and washed with chloroform. The filtrate together with the washings was evaporated under reduced pressure. The red thick oil solidified on cooling. It was recrystallised from ethylacetate, m.p. 83° (1.5 g.). (Found: C, 59.7; H, 6.24. $C_{11}H_{11}O_2N.H_2O$ requires C, 59.2; H, 5.8%) The *N*-oxide afforded a yellow picrate from *n*-butanol in needles, m.p. 173°. (Found: C, 47.3; H, 3.1. $C_{11}H_{11}O_3N.C_6H_5O_7N_3$ requires C, 47.0; H, 3.2%.)

The foregoing *N*-oxide (1.0 g.) was taken with $POCl_3$ (10 ml.) and refluxed for 6 hr. The excess of the oxychloride was removed and the residue treated with crushed ice. The solution was extracted with ether; the extract was dried ($MgSO_4$) and evaporated to provide 1-chloro-7,8-dimethoxyisoquinoline which was crystallised from light petroleum, m.p. 95-96°. (Found: C, 58.8; H, 5.1. $C_{11}H_{11}O_2NCl$ requires C, 59.0; H, 4.9%). It formed a yellow picrate, m.p. 141-42°.

3-Ethoxy-4-methoxyphthalide.—2-Ethoxy-3-methoxybenzoic acid (9.8 g.), prepared by ethylation and subsequent oxidation of *o*-vanillin, was taken with HCl (conc., 40 ml.) and formaldehyde (4 ml., 40%) and saturated with dry HCl gas at 0° . The solution was complete and it assumed a brownish red colour. It was stirred at the room temperature for 4 hr. and then left overnight. Next day the solution was concentrated to some extent, when a brown oil separated. The solution was cooled and its pH was brought to 3-4 by NaOH solution. The clear solution was decanted from the gum adhering to the wall of the vessel. The gum was triturated with sodium bicarbonate solution, when it yielded a slightly brown granular solid (6 g.), m.p. 61-62°. Recrystallisation with light petroleum furnished color-

less crystals, m.p. 70-71°, of 3-ethoxy-4-methoxyphthalide. The phthalide was always accompanied by a persistent impurity containing halogen. (Found: C, 63.02; H, 6.1. $C_{11}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 63.46; H, 5.76%).

2-Ethoxy-3-methoxy-6-aldehydobenzoic Acid.—The phthalide (3.0 g.) was taken with water (130 ml.), warmed and active manganese dioxide (5 g.) was added to it. H_2SO_4 (4 ml. in 7.5 ml. water) was added dropwise with stirring and the contents were heated for 3 hr. On cooling the solution, some colorless crystals were obtained which were filtered. The mother liquor was concentrated to half its bulk and left to cool in a refrigerator when more crystals of the acid, mixed with some unchanged phthalide, were obtained. This was filtered and the combined residue was treated with sodium bicarbonate solution and filtered. The filtrate on acidification with HCl (conc.) afforded the colorless crystalline acid (0.9 g.) m.p. 131-32°. It was recrystallised from water, m.p. 132-33°. (Found: C, 59.43; H, 6.0. $C_{11}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 58.93; H, 5.99%). The compound gave vermilion red DNP, m.p. 236-37° decomp.) from ethanol. (Found: N, 13.9. $C_{17}H_{16}O_8N_4$ requires N, 13.8%).

The acid (1.0 g.) was esterified with diazomethane (from nitrosomethylurea 1.5 g.). The resulting ester was a thick oil (0.9 g.) which could not be induced to crystallise. The derived semicarbazone melted at 198° (from EtOH). (Found: C, 52.5; H, 5.9, N, 14.5. $C_{11}H_{11}O_5N_3$ requires C, 52.8; H, 5.7; N, 14.2%).

7-Methoxy-8-ethoxyisocarbostyryl-3-carboxylic Acid.—The aforesaid ester (0.9 g.) was mixed with powdered hippuric acid (1.0 g.), fused sodium acetate (0.4 g.), and acetic anhydride (2.3 ml.) and the mixture left on a water bath for 3 hr. The clear red solution was decomposed with water (5 ml.) and the gummy mass was treated with acetic acid, when orange-red crystals of the 2-phenyl-4-(2'-methoxycarbonyl-3'-ethoxy-4'-methoxy) benzylidene-5-oxazolone separated (0.6 g.) It was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 167-68°. (Found: C, 66.9; H, 5.1. $C_{21}H_{19}O_8N$ requires C, 66.1; H, 4.9%).

The oxazolone (0.5 g.) was taken with 10% KOH solution (7 ml.) and heated on a water bath for 45 min. The clear yellow solution was cooled and acidified with HCl (conc.), filtered, and washed with hot water. 7-Methoxy-8-ethoxyisocarbostyryl-3-carboxylic acid melted at 257-8° (from acetic acid). (Found: C, 59.0; H, 5.3. $C_{21}H_{19}O_8N$ requires C, 59.3; H, 4.9%).

Ethyl 7-Methoxy-8-hydroxyisocarbostyryl-3-carboxylate.—The preceding acid (0.1 g.) was heated in a metal bath at 270-80° for 10 min. when it turned to a tranquil dark melt. On sublimation in vacuum and thoroughly washing the reaction product with sodium bicarbonate solution and water, a compound, m.p. 203-4° was obtained. Recrystallization with glacial acetic acid furnished light violet needles of the ester, m.p. 207°. It showed a deep green ferric reaction. (Found: C, 58.9; H, 5.4. $C_{13}H_{13}O_5N$ requires C, 59.3; H, 4.9%).

Hydrolysis. The preceding ester (0.02 g.) was taken in 10% K_2CO_3 solution (1 ml.) and heated on a water bath for 3 hr. The potassium salt separated within an hour and a half. After cooling and acidification with HCl (conc.) a brown solid was obtained, m.p. 310-11°. It sublimed to afford a product, m.p. and mixed m.p. with 7-methoxy-8-hydroxyisocarbostyryl-3-carboxylic acid, 314-15° (no depression).

7-Methoxy-8-ethoxyisocoumarin-3-carboxylic Acid.—2-Ethoxy-3-methoxy-6-aldehydobenzoic acid (0.9 g.), ethyl bromomalonate (1.0 g.) and freshly baked potassium carbonate

(1.5 g.) were taken in dry ethyl methyl ketone (20 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for 3 hr. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the residue treated with water, extracted with ether, the ethereal extract washed with water, and dried over $MgSO_4$. On evaporation of the solvent, a light yellow thick gum was obtained which solidified slowly, m.p. 83° (1.48 g.).

The above compound was taken with acetic acid (5 ml.) HCl (conc., 3 ml.), and water (2 ml.) and refluxed for 1 hr. The acid was obtained on cooling as a pale yellow light solid (0.6 g.). It was recrystallised from acetic acid in light yellow needles, m.p. $244-45^\circ$. (Found: C, 58.9; H, 4.9. $C_{13}H_{11}O_6$ requires C, 59.09; H, 4.5 %). On prolonging the period of hydrolysis, the acid undergoes gradual de-ethylation.

The ethyl ester of the preceding acid was obtained by refluxing the acid with ethanol and H_2SO_4 ; m.p. 145° (from ethanol). (Found: C, 61.1; H, 5.6. $C_{13}H_{16}O_6$ requires C, 61.7; H, 5.4%).

The above isocoumarin acid (0.05 g.) was taken in ethanolic ammonia (5 ml., saturated at 0°) and left in a pressure bottle for 12 hr. On working up the solution in usual manner, 7-methoxy-8-ethoxyisocarbostyryl-3-carboxylic acid, m.p. $256-7^\circ$ was obtained. Mixed m.p. with the authentic sample remained undepressed.

Decarboxylation of 7-Methoxy-8-ethoxyisocoumarin-3-carboxylic Acid.—The acid (0.6 g.) was intimately mixed with copper bronze (0.06 g.) and heated in a metal bath till the evolution of CO_2 was complete (15-20 min.). The product, on distillation, yielded light yellow oil which solidified slowly (0.39 g.). This melted in a range and showed a green ferric reaction. The whole of the distillate was taken in ether and washed with saturated sodium bicarbonate solution to remove the unchanged acid, if any. The ethereal solution was then washed thrice with 3 c.c. portions of 0.5% NaOH solution. On keeping, the washing began turning green and hence taken directly into HCl (conc.). This provided a colorless product recrystallising from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. $150-51^\circ$ (lit.⁸ m.p. $150-51^\circ$). Its analysis agreed with 7-methoxy-8-hydroxyisocoumarin; and mixed m.p. with the authentic sample remained undepressed. (Found: C, 62.1; H, 4.3. Calc. for $C_{10}H_8O_4$: C, 62.5; H, 4.16%).

The ethereal layer was washed with water, dried over $MgSO_4$ and evaporated to afford a low melting solid (0.2 g.), m.p. $63-64^\circ$. This was recrystallised from petroleum ($60-80^\circ$) in colorless plates, m.p. $67-68^\circ$ and was identified as 7-Methoxy-8-ethoxyisocoumarin. (Found: C, 65.01; H, 5.8. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{12}O_4$: C, 65.4; H, 5.4%)

Ethylation of 7-Methoxy-8-hydroxyisocoumarin.—7-Methoxy-8-hydroxyisocoumarin (0.015 g.) was taken with ethyl iodide (1.0 ml.) and freshly baked potassium carbonate (1.0 g.) in dry acetone (10 ml.) and refluxed overnight. The solution was filtered; on working up the filtrate in usual manner, the isocoumarin, m.p. 67° , was obtained. Mixed m.p. with the above sample remained undepressed.

7-Methoxy-8-ethoxyisocarbostyryl.—The preceding isocoumarin (0.05 g.) was taken with ethanolic ammonia (5 ml., saturated at 0°) and left for 48 hr. in a pressure bottle. On working up in the usual manner, a viscous oil was obtained which was crystallised from petroleum ($60-80^\circ$) in colorless needles, m.p. 132° . (Found: C, 65.5; H, 5.9. $C_{11}H_{12}O_4N$ requires C, 65.8; H, 5.9%)

It formed a yellow *picrate* in ethanolic solution, m. p. 180°. (Found: N, 12.9. $C_{12}H_{13}O_5N_2C_6H_3O_7N_3$ requires N, 12.5%.)

6,7-Dimethoxyisocarbostryll 3-carboxylic Acid.—*m*-Opianic acid was prepared from veratric acid by way of *m*-mesonine, according to the method of Edward *et al.*¹², also Newbold and Brown¹³. The acid (1.5 g.) was esterified with diazomethane (from nitrosomethylurea 2.0 g.). The ester (1.5 g.) was treated with hippuric acid (1.363 g.), fused sodium acetate (0.454 g.), and acetic anhydride (3.2 ml.) and heated on a water bath for 3 hr. 2-Phenyl-4-(2'-carboxymethyl-4', 5'-dimethoxy)-benzylidene-5-oxazolone separated in a few minutes. The excess of the acetic anhydride was decomposed with water, filtered, and the oxazolone recrystallised from acetic acid in yellow needles (1.5 g.), m. p. 200°. Found: N, 3.6. $C_{20}H_{17}O_6N$ requires N, 3.81%.

The oxazolone (1.5 g.) was taken with 10% aqueous KOH (23 ml.) and heated on a water bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. It was then acidified with HCl (conc.) when an amorphous product was obtained which was crystallised from a large volume of acetic acid, m. p. 313-14° (decomp.) (0.6 g.). The same product was obtained by treating 6,7-dimethoxyisocoumarin-3-carboxylic acid (*vide infra*) with ammonia. (Found: C, 57.6; H, 5.0. $C_{12}H_{11}O_5N$ requires C, 57.8; H, 4.4%.)

Decarboxylation

(i) *By Simple Heating.*—The aforesaid acid (0.1 g.) was heated in a metal bath at 320-40° (for 15 min.) till the evolution of the gas had visibly ceased. The product was sublimed in vacuum when a larger portion of the compound was decomposed and only a little of the sublimate was obtained. The sublimate on thorough washing with sodium bicarbonate solution and crystallisation with benzene melted at m. p. 233-34° (3-4 mg.).

(ii) *With Copper-bronze.*—The acid (0.1 g.) was mixed intimately with copper bronze (0.02 g.) and heated for 15 min. at 320-40° in a metal bath. The residue worked up in the usual manner and crystallised from benzene, m. p. 233-34° (5 mg.).

(iii) *With Copper-bronze-quinoline.*—The acid (0.2 g.) was taken with copper bronze (0.1 g.) and quinoline (3 ml.), and refluxed for 3 hr. The quinoline was removed by steam distillation and the reaction mixture extracted with ether; the extract was washed with sodium bicarbonate and dried over $MgSO_4$. On evaporation of ether, a solid product was obtained which was recrystallised from benzene in colorless needles, m. p. 235-36° (0.06 g.). (Found: C, 63.8; H, 5.9. $C_{11}H_{11}O_5N$ requires C, 64.3; H, 5.4%). λ_{max}^{EtOH} 245, 279, 270 μ . The *picrate* crystallised from ethanol, m. p. 208°. (Found: N, 13.3. $C_{11}H_{11}O_5N.C_6H_3O_7N_3$ requires N, 12.9%).

6,7-Dimethoxyisocoumarin-3-carboxylic Acid

(i) *m*-Opianic acid (2.0 g.) and ethyl bromomalonate (2.0 g.) were dissolved in methyl ethyl ketone (30 ml.) containing freshly baked potassium carbonate (3.0 g.); The mixture was refluxed for 3 hr., the solvent removed, water was added, and extracted with a large volume of ether. On removal of ether, shining prismatic crystals of 3,3-diethoxycarbonyl-4-hydroxy-3,4-dihydro-6,7-dimethoxyisocoumarin separated, m. p. 153-54°. The IR spectrum showed carbonyl absorption at 5.68 μ , 5.78 μ .

12. Edward *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 196.

13. Newbold and Brown, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 4397.

On boiling the aforesaid compound HCl with (conc., 6 ml.) and acetic acid (10 ml.) for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr., crystals of the acid (1.0 g.) separated, m.p. 295-96°.

(ii) A solution of dimethyl 4,5-dimethoxyhomophthalate (1.5 g.) in benzene (19 ml.) and ethyl oxalate (0.9 g.) was added to cooled dry sodium methoxide (from sodium, 0.15 g.). The mixture was kept overnight. Next day, this was treated with water, and the aqueous portion acidified with HCl and extracted with ether. On evaporation of the solvent, the oxalyl derivative was obtained as an oil which was cyclised by warming with a drop of HCl (conc.) and two drops of acetic acid for 5 min. 3-ethoxycarbonyl-4-methoxycarbonyl-6,7-dimethoxy isocoumarin (1.4 g.) separated on cooling. It was crystallised from acetic acid in colorless leaflets, m.p. 100°. (Found: C, 57.00; H, 4.0. $C_{16}H_{16}O_8$ requires C, 57.16; H, 4.8%).

The foregoing ester (1.2 g.) was dissolved in a mixture of acetic acid (2 ml.) and HCl (conc., 3 ml) and was refluxed for 3 hr. On cooling, the acid (0.6 g.) separated which was crystallised from acetic acid in cream-coloured leaflets, m.p. 295° (with slow gas evolution). (Found: C, 57.70; H, 3.82. $C_{16}H_{16}O_8$ requires C, 57.61; H, 4.00 %).

6,7-Dimethoxyisocoumarin-3-carboxylic acid (1.0 g.) was intimately mixed with copper-bronze (0.05 g.) and heated in a metal bath at 310° till the evolution of CO_2 had ceased. The product was distilled in high vacuum to provide 6,7-dimethoxyisocoumarin (0.6 g.) crystallising from light petroleum as prisms, m.p. 97° (I.R. absorption at 5.92 μ). Found: C, 63.9; H, 4.0. $C_{11}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 64.07; H, 4.8 %).

The isocoumarin (0.23 g.) was treated with ethanolic ammonia (15 ml. saturated at 0°), in a pressure bottle for 3 days. The solution evaporated to dryness on a water bath to furnish 6, 7-dimethoxyisocarbostyryl as colorless crystalline solid, m.p. 231°. Recrystallised from benzene it melted at 235-36°, mixed m.p. with the authentic sample remained undepressed.

Synthesis of 6, 7-Dimethoxyisoquinoline.—The isocarbostyryl (0.2 g.) was treated with $POCl_3$ (5 ml.) and refluxed for 4 hr. The excess of the oxyphloride removed in vacuum and the residue treated with ice and the mixture was made alkaline with ammonium hydroxide solution, when the 1-chloro-6, 7-dimethoxyisoquinoline was obtained as a crystalline precipitate, forming a yellow picrate from ethanol, m.p. 193-04° (lit.¹⁴, m.p. 190-91°). (Found: N, 12.67. calc. for $C_{11}H_{10}O_4NCl \cdot C_6H_5O_7N_3$: N, 12.36%).

The foregoing compound (0.05 g.) was taken in methanol (5 ml.) and reduced catalytically over palladised charcoal (10%) in presence of a drop of methanolic KOH solution. The reduction was complete in about 10 min. The solution was filtered, evaporated to dryness; a little of water was added to it and extracted with ether. The ethereal layer dried over $MgSO_4$ and evaporated to dryness. The impure 6,7-dimethoxyisoquinoline was obtained as a semi-solid mass which was converted to the picrate, m.p. 223-24° (from ethanol) (lit.¹⁵, m.p. 225-26°)

2-Isonitroso-4, 7-dimethoxy-1-hydrindone.—4,7-Dimethoxyindan-1-one (10 g.) was taken in methanol (75 ml.) and HCl (conc., 15 ml.) and to the fine suspension was passed methyl nitrite gas for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. The mixture was left for some time to cool at laboratory

14. Anderson *et al*, *J. Am. Pharm. Assoc. Sci. Ed.*, 1952, 41, 643.

15. Karvas and Tihlarik, Slovenska akad. vied, Bratislava, (Czech) *Chem. Zvesti*, 1960, 14, 529, *Chem. Abstr.* 1961, 55, 16553.

temperature and the *isonitroso* compound was filtered (7 g.) m.p. 237-38° (decomp.) Found: C, 59.1; H, 5.5. $C_{11}H_{11}O_4N$ requires C, 59.7; H, 4.9 %).

2-Carboxy-3, 6-dimethoxyphenylacetonitrile. The *isonitroso* compound (2.5 g.) was taken with 10% solution of NaOH (25 ml.) and warmed at 40° on a water bath. Tosyl chloride (3 g.) was added portionwise and finally the reaction was completed by raising the temperature to 80°. The mixture was cooled and filtered; the filtrate on acidification with HCl (conc.) provided the *nitrile* (1.5 g.). It was recrystallized from water in slightly coloured needles, m.p. 142-43°. (Found: C, 59.5; H, 5.3. $C_{11}H_{11}O_4N$ requires C, 59.7; H, 4.9 %).

3,6-Dimethoxyhomophthalic Acid.—The crude nitrile (1.5 g.), was dissolved in 10% solution of NaOH (8 ml.) and refluxed on a sand bath for 7 hr. It was then cooled, filtered and acidified with HCl (conc.) The acidified solution on continuous ether extraction afforded the *acid* (1.4 g.) which recrystallised from water in colourless needles, m.p. 168-69°. (Found: C, 54.8; H, 5.1. $C_{11}H_{10}O_6$ requires C, 55.0; H, 5.0 %).

Dimethyl 3, 6-Dimethoxyhomophthalate.—The foregoing acid (4.8 g.) was esterified with diazomethane and the ester distilled at 152°/1 mm as a light yellow oil (4.5 g.) which did not crystallize. (Found: C, 57.80; H, 6.1. $C_{13}H_{16}O_6$ requires C, 58.20; H, 6.01 %). IR spectrum: 5.759 μ (ester carbonyl) (thin film).

5,8-Dimethoxyisocoumarin-3-carboxylic Acid.—The aforesaid ester (3.2 g.) and freshly distilled diethyl oxalate (1.92 g.) were taken in dry benzene (40 ml.) and added to cooled anhydrous sodium methoxide (from 0.32 g. of sodium). The solution turned reddish yellow and sodium methoxide gradually went into solution. The mixture was kept for 45 hr. at the room temperature and worked up after heating at 50-60° for 1 hr. The benzene layer was extracted twice with 1% solution of NaOH (10 ml.) and the aqueous alkaline layer acidified with HCl (conc.) A yellow oil separated which was extracted with ether and the extract dried over $MgSO_4$. On evaporation of the solvent, an oil (0.5 g.) was obtained.

The oil was taken in acetic acid (4 ml.) and HCl (conc. 0 ml.) and refluxed for 3 hr. Some acetic acid was removed under reduced pressure and then the solution cooled, when 5, 8-dimethoxyisocoumarin-3-carboxylic acid, (0.2 g.) was obtained. It was recrystallised from ethanol into yellow needles, m.p. 264-65° (IR absorption at 5.79 μ , 5.95 μ). (Found: C, 57.1; H, 4.4. $C_{14}H_{10}O_6$ requires C, 57.6; H, 4.0 %). Unchanged homophthalic ester (2.3 g.) was recovered from the benzene solution.

5, 8-Dimethoxyisocarbostyryl-3-carboxylic Acid.—The above isocoumarin acid (0.145 g.) was taken in ethanolic ammonia (5 ml. saturated at 0°) and left for 24 hr. in a pressure bottle. The ethanol evaporated and the residue acidified with HCl (dil.), warmed a little on a water bath, cooled and filtered. The acid (0.12 g.) obtained was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 274-75° (decomp.) (IR absorption at 5.91 μ). (Found: C, 57.3; H, 4.7. $C_{16}H_{11}O_5N$ requires C, 57.8; H, 4.4 %). The acid developed a light brown colour. with ferric chloride.

Methyl 5-Methoxy-8-hydroxyisocarbostyryl-3-carboxylate.—The 5,8-dimethoxyisocarbostyryl-3-carboxylic acid (0.05 g.) was heated in a metal bath at 290-90°, when the acid melted and slight gas evolution also took place. Instantaneously some yellow sublimate also began depositing on the cooler parts of the reaction vessel. The whole substance on being sublimed in vacuum deposited yellow crystalline particles on the cold finger. The

product was scraped out and triturated with sodium bicarbonate solution, filtered, and washed with water. It was recrystallised from ethanol in slender yellow needles, m.p. 243-4° (I.R. spectrum showed ester carbonyl absorption at 5.79 μ). (Found: C, 57.3; H, 5.0. $C_{12}H_{11}O_5N$ requires C, 57.8; H, 4.4%). The compound is soluble in warm alkali (10% NaOH, 10% K_2CO_3). It showed a deep green ferric reaction.

5,8-Dimethoxyisocoumarin.—A solution of methyl 3,6-dimethoxyhomophthalate (1.5 g.) in dry ether (15 ml.) was mixed with methyl formate (7 ml.) and the mixture added slowly to cool dry sodium methoxide (from sodium 0.35 g.). The mixture was left overnight at the room temperature. Next day, more of ether and methyl formate (3 ml.) were added and the mixture was shaken. After sometime white solid particles began to separate. The mixture was further shaken at intervals and left for 40 hr. in all. The solvent removed and the mass treated with water when practically the whole amount went into solution.

The solution was acidified with HCl (conc.) and warmed on a water bath for 15 min., but 4-methoxycarbonyl-5,8-dimethoxyisocoumarin did not crystallise. This ester was extracted with ether, dried over $MgSO_4$ and evaporated to dryness when (1.0 g.) of a thick gum was obtained. This was boiled with a mixture of acetic acid (10 ml.) and HCl (conc., 30 ml) for 4 hr. After removal of the acids under reduced pressure the residue was taken up in ether. The ether solution was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and dried over $MgSO_4$. The residue on removal of ether was distilled in vacuum to afford a light yellow oil (0.6 g.) which proved to be a mixture (on account of partial demethylation).

The product (0.1 g.) was taken in ether (15 ml.) and washed with 0.5% NaOH solution (5 $\times$ 2 ml.); the washings were acidified with HCl (dil.). A colorless precipitate was obtained which was filtered and crystallised from benzene-light petroleum in long, colorless, fine needles, m.p. 127-28° (0.04 g.) of 5-methoxy-8-hydroxyisocoumarin. (IR absorption of associated carbonyl at 5.96 μ). Found: C, 62.5; H, 4.8. $C_{10}H_8O_4$ requires C, 62.52; H, 4.2%.

The ether solution was washed with water, dried over $MgSO_4$ and evaporated to provide fine colorless needles of 5,8-Dimethoxyisocoumarin which crystallised from benzene-light petroleum in colorless needles, m.p. 102-3° (0.03 g.) (I.R. spectrum 5.84 μ). (Found: C, 63.03; H, 4.8. $C_{11}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 64.0; H, 4.7%).

5,8-Dimethoxy-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin.—5,8-Dimethoxyisocoumarin (0.05 g.) in acetic acid (2 ml.) was hydrogenated in presence of palladised charcoal (30%) at the room temperature and atmospheric pressure, when one mole of hydrogen was consumed. After filtration, the solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the residue diluted with some drops of water, when the 5,8-dimethoxy-3,4-dihydro isocoumarin was obtained in quantitative yield. It was recrystallised from ethyl acetate-light petroleum in colorless cubes, m.p. 87-88°. Even on repeated crystallisations the m.p. did not rise (lit.¹⁶, m.p. 90°) (IR absorption at 5.84 μ).^{*} (Found: C, 63.3; H, 6.1 Calc. for $C_{11}H_{12}O_4$, C, 63.40, H, 5.7%).

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16. Choudhury and Banerjee, *This Journal* 1962, 39, 249.

*A specimen kindly provided by Prof. D. N. Choudhury melted at 87-88° and had identical IR spectrum.